

Bilateral macro nodular adrenal hyperplasia causing primary hyperaldosteronism and Cushing syndrome

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Abstract

The coexistence of primary hyperaldosteronism and Cushing's syndrome in the same patient is an uncommon situation.

We report the case of a 35-year-old female patient with resistant hypertension since the age of 30 years in whom exploration revealed a combination of primary hyperaldosteronism and ACTH-independent Cushing syndrome in the context of bilateral macro nodular adrenal hyperplasia.

G protein-coupled receptors aberrantly expressed in the adrenal cortex appear to have a central role in hormone hypersecretion and cell proliferation in this disease. However, other molecular mechanisms - such as mutations in Gsp or ACTH receptors, and adrenal paracrine hormone secretion may also be involved in this disease.

A good understanding of this rare and heterogeneous disease entity has contributed to a more accurate assessment of patients with PBMAH, improving earlier diagnosis and offering new therapeutic and potentially preventive strategies.

Keywords: Primary bilateral macro nodular adrenal hyperplasia (PBMAH); Cushing's syndrome; Autonomous cortisol secretion; Aberrant receptors; ARMC5

1. Introduction

Primary hyperaldosteronism (PAH) is characterized by hypertension, whether or not associated with hypokalemia, and is thought to affect 10% of hypertensive patients. It is mainly due to an adenoma or hyperplasia. Subclinical cortisol adenomas are benign tumors producing cortisol in an autonomous way that can slow down the corticotrophic axis and the contralateral adrenal gland to varying degrees.

Primary hyperaldosteronism and Cushing's syndrome are two endocrine pathologies that may cause secondary hypertension (hypertension), possibly associated with hypokalemia. They often occur separately. Their coexistence in the same patient is an uncommon situation, which can be seen in the context of adrenal lesion.

Primary bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia (PBMAH) accounts for <1% of Cushing's syndrome causes (1). Primary aldosteronism (PA) characterized by autonomous aldosterone hypersecretion constitutes mainly two subtypes, aldosterone-producing adenoma (APA) and bilateral idiopathic hyperaldosteronism (IHA). PA is currently considered to be a more common disease causing secondary hypertension than previously believed; its prevalence among hypertensive patients has been reported to be 5-15% (2). However, to date only a few cases of PA with Cushing's

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Syndrom due to a primary bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia co-secreting aldosterone and cortisol have been reported (4, 6-8).

2. Case report

We report the case of a combination of primary hyperaldosteronism (basal Aldosterone 1035 pmol/L, Renin 9.6 mIU/L, RAR 108 and clinical and biological ACTH independent cushing syndrome: CLU = 333 ug/24h (4.5 times normal), negative dexamethasone minute braking test (cortisol=17.7), ACTH braked at 1, 3 pg/mL with the presence of multiple bilateral adrenal nodules > 1 cm in diameter with benign looking adrenal cortex hyperplasia on CT, nor-iodo-cholesterol scintigraphy and adrenal vein catheterization not performed. In a 35-year-old patient, hypertensive for 5 years with moderate hypokalemia, the patient is taking an antihypertensive quadritherapy including a spironolactone with improvement of the blood pressure figures and normalization of the hypokalemia.

Therefore, the diagnosis of bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia with aldosterone-cortisol cosecretion was retained and a bilateral surrenalectomy in 2 times was indicated.

In the absence of catheterization of the adrenal veins and a nor-iodo-cholesterol scintigraphy, the left adrenalectomy was performed in a first step (size criterion), the anatomo-pathological study confirmed the diagnosis of BMAH.

3. Discussion

Bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia (PBMAH) is a very rare cause of endogenous ACTH-independent cushing syndrome (<2%).

PBMAH has a characteristic imaging appearance of multiple bilateral macronodules (>10 mm) with hyperplasia and adrenal cortex.

Pathophysiologically, the expression of aberrant membrane receptors in the adrenal cortex plays an important role. In most cases, PBMAH is a sporadic disorder, although familial cases have been described.(9)

Recent studies have shown an association between germline/somatic mutations of the tumor suppressor gene ARMC5 in about 50% of cases.(10).

3.1. Genetic causes of PBMAH

In the majority of cases PBMAH appears to be sporadic. Several reports of familial clustering have been published with an autosomal dominant pattern of transmission.(11–15) The prevalence of familial forms of AIMAH is not yet known, as systematic familial screening has not been conducted. In recently studied families with PBMAH, aberrant hormone receptors have been identified in their adrenal tissues (see later section), but the genes implicated have not yet been identified.(16–17).Bilateral adrenal enlargement was found in 21% of a series of 33 patients with multiple endocrine neoplasia type-1 syndrome (MEN-1). In a large kindred of MEN-1, the prevalence of bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia was 6%. No sporadic somatic mutation of the Menin gene has been identified in adrenocortical tissue in AIMAH. Bilateral adrenal nodules have also been found in patients with familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP), but a somatic point mutation of the APC gene was not found. In one report, AIMAH was identified in a patient with hereditary leiomyomatosis and renal cell cancer disorder due to a mutation in the fumaratehydratase gene (FH).

Adrenal adenomas are generally monosecretory. However, a mixed secretion can be observed in some cases, in our case, it is a hypersecretion of aldosterone and cortisol. Such a functional data seems important in a context of primary hyperaldosteronism because an associated hypercorticism, even infraclinical, leads to an increase in bone and metabolic morbidity with a risk of postoperative adrenal insufficiency in ignorance of the diagnosis. Some studies have found a 10% frequency of cosecretion, thus justifying the systematic search for cortisolichypersecretion in the presence of primary hyperaldosteronism.

Bilateral laparoscopic adrenalectomy is the main treatment for BMAH (18), In 45 bilateral adrenalectomies for BMAH, no surgery related death was noted. Because bilateral laparoscopic adrenalectomy requires lifelong steroid replacement and may induce adrenal insufficiency crisis, unilateral adrenalectomy was proposed in selected cases. Remission was achieved by unilateral adrenalectomy in patients with mild Cushing's syndrome. A study (15) reported a 93% success rate from unilateral adrenalectomy with a median follow-up of 69 months; two patients experienced transient

symptoms of hypocortisolism. UFC more than two times the upper limit of normal and marked asymmetry of adrenal enlargement are the best predictors of unilateral adrenalectomy effectiveness (18).

Figure 1 Hypothesis of sequential genetic events leading to AIMAH

Table 1 Principal genes associated to BMAH (18)

Gene	Locus	Action	Type of mutation
ARMCS5	16p11.2	Causes apoptosis and adrenal cell death	Germline and somatic
MEN-1	11q13	Regulation of cell proliferation and differentiation	Germline
APC	5q12-22	Prevention of β -catenin accumulation	Germline
PDE11A	2q31-35	Catalyzes the hydrolysis of cAMP and cGMP	Germline inactivation
GNAS	20q13.1	Stimulates cAMP production	Somatic during embryogenesis
MC2R	18p11.2	Regulates cortisol production and adrenal growth	Somatic
FH	1q42.1	Involved in Krebs cycle (mitochondria) and amino acid metabolism (cytosol)	Germline

ARMCS5, armadillo repeat containing 5; APC, adenomatous poliposis coli; GNAS, stimulatory G-protein alpha subunit; MC2R, melanocortin 2 receptor; MEN1, multiple endocrine neoplasia 1; PDE11A, 11A phosphodiesterase isoform.

4. Conclusion

The coexistence of primary hyperaldosteronism and cushing’s syndrome in the same patient is an uncommon situation, which can be seen in the context of an adrenal lesion, including an adrenal nodule secreting both hormones: aldosterone and cortisol; the presence of a bilateral lesion such as the primary bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia (PBMAH) is even more rare.

Thus justifying the systematic search for cortisolichypersecretion in the presence of primary hyperaldosteronism.

In recent years, several new findings have contributed to a better understanding of the heterogeneity of pathogenesis in PBMAH. Aberrantly expressed G-protein-coupled receptors in the adrenal cortex appear to have a central role in the hormonal hypersecretion and cell proliferation in this disease. However, other molecular mechanisms can also be implicated in this disease.

The appropriate surgical management of PBMAH remains controversial. Bilateral adrenalectomy results in lifelong steroid dependence. And is best reserved for patients with severe Cushing’s syndrome. Unilateral adrenalectomy may be considered in selected patients.

The molecular and genetic findings identified recently should allow making early diagnosis and identify new targets to develop personalized pharmaceutical therapy. It is likely that other genes implicated in the development of BMAH will be identified. Genetic screening should allow identifying mutation carriers. Longitudinal follow-up of larger cohorts of patients in an international collaborative effort should define the natural history and indications for intervention therapies in these patients.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Thanking the patient for consent to describe her clinical case for the purpose of continuing education.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from the patient included in the study.

References

- [1] A. Lacroix / Best Practice & Research Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism 23 (2009) 245–259
- [2] Aarskog D & Tveteraas E. McCune-Albright's syndrome following adrenalectomy for Cushing's syndrome in infancy. The Journal of Pediatrics 1968; 73: 89–96.
- [3] Benjamin DR & McRoberts JW. Polyostotic fibrous dysplasia associated with Cushing syndrome. Archives of Pathology 1973; 96: 175–178.
- [4] MacMahon HE. Albright's syndrome—thirty years later. (Polyostotic fibrous dysplasia). Pathology Annual 1971; 6: 81–146.
- [5] Danon M, Robboy SJ, Kim S et al. Cushing syndrome, sexual precocity, and polyostotic fibrous dysplasia (Albright syndrome) in infancy. The Journal of Pediatrics 1975; 87: 917–921.
- [6] Fragoso MC, Domenice S, Latronico AC et al. Cushing's syndrome secondary to adrenocorticotropin-independent macronodular adrenocortical hyperplasia due to activating mutations of GNAS1 gene. The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism 2003; 88: 2147–2151.
- [7] Lacroix A, Baldacchino V, Bourdeau I et al. Cushing's syndrome variants secondary to aberrant hormone receptors. Trends in Endocrinology and Metabolism 2004; 15: 375–382.
- [8] Bertagna X, Groussin L, Luton J-P et al. Aberrant receptor-mediated Cushing's syndrome. Hormone Research 2003; 59(Suppl. 1): 99–103.
- [9] Nawata H, Demura H, Suda T, Takayanagi R. Adrenal preclinical Cushing's syndrome. In: Annual Report of the Ministry of Health and Welfare [Disorders of Adrenal Hormones]. Research Committee, Japan, 1996: 223–226 (in Japanese).
- [10] Zwermann O, Suttman Y, Bidlingmaier M, Beuschlein F, Reincke M. Screening for membrane hormone receptor expression in primary aldosteronism. Eur J Endocrinol 160: 443–451, 2009.
- [11] Lampron A, Bourdeau I, Oble S, et al. Regulation of aldosterone secretion by several aberrant receptors including for glucose-dependent insulinotropic peptide in a patient with an aldosteronoma. J Clin Endocrinol Metab 94: 750–756, 2009.
- [12] Libe R, Coste J, Guignat L, et al. Aberrant cortisol regulations in bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia: a frequent finding in a prospective study of 32 patients with overt or subclinical Cushing's syndrome. Eur J Endocrinol 2010; 163:129–138.
- [13] Hofland J, Hofland LJ, van Koetsveld PM, et al. ACTH-independent macronodular adrenocortical hyperplasia reveals prevalent aberrant in vivo and in vitro responses to hormonal stimuli and coupling of arginine-vasopressin type 1a receptor to 11b-hydroxylase. Orphanet J Rare Dis 2013; 8:142.
- [14] Hsiao HP, Kirschner LS, Bourdeau I, et al. Clinical and genetic heterogeneity, overlap with other tumor syndromes, and atypical glucocorticoid hormone secretion in adrenocorticotropin-independent macronodular adrenal hyperplasia compared with other adrenocortical tumors. J Clin End Metabol 2009; 94:2930–2937.

- [15] Assie´ G, Libe´ R, Espiard S, et al. ARMC5 mutations in macronodular adrenal hyperplasia with Cushing’s syndrome. *N Engl J Med* 2013; 369:2105–2114. This study identifies germline and somatic mutations of ARMC5 in apparently sporadic BMAH patients; it identifies that BMAH is more frequently genetically determined than previously believed. Initial functional studies indicate that ARMC5 behaves as a tumor suppressor gene.
- [16] Alencar GA, Lerario AM, Nishi MY, et al. ARMC5 mutations are a frequent cause of ACTH-independent macronodular adrenal hyperplasia. *J Clin End Metabol* 2014. [Epub ahead of print].
- [17] Assie G, Louiset E, Sturm N, et al. Systematic analysis of G protein-coupled receptor gene expression in adrenocorticotropin-independent macronodular adrenocortical hyperplasia identifies novel targets for pharmacological control of adrenal Cushing’s syndrome. *J ClinEndocrinolMetab* 2010; 95:E253– E262.
- [18] Agostino De Venanzia ,GuilhermeAsmarAlencarb et all, Primary bilateral macronodular adrenal hyperplasia, *CurrOpinEndocrinol Diabetes Obes* 2014, 21:177–184.